

**DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION AND ACCEPTANCE
OF A MODULE FOR HOUSEKEEPING
SPECIALIZATION IN TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL
LIVELIHOOD TRACK OF THE SENIOR HIGH
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Development, Validation and Acceptance of a Module for Housekeeping Specialization in Technical Vocational Livelihood Track of the Senior High School Education

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Abstract

The objective of this research was to create a housekeeping module for teachers and students in senior high schools using the process Analysis, Design, Development and Evaluation or ADDIE instructional model design, but it was limited to Implementation. TVL teachers from varied strands and specializations, TVL supervisor and TESDA experts from tourism sector assessed its level of acceptance and validity. It was conducted in 19 senior high schools with TVL track in the Division of Marinduque. This study used an adapted and validated questionnaire to determine the level of validity in terms of content, organization, relevance, clarity and appropriateness of exercise, and the level of acceptability in terms of objectives, contents, organizations, graphics and relevance. The content and design of the module was evaluated and assessed by TVL teachers, TESDA experts and TVL supervisor. With the use of percentage and computation of mean as the statistical tools in computing the numerical data, as well as its standard deviation, the researcher found out that the module's validity is "Very Much Valid". On the other hand, when it comes to the acceptability, it was found out that the module is "Highly Acceptable". Based on these findings, it was then concluded that the developed module in Housekeeping complies with the level of validity in terms of content, organization, relevance, clarity and appropriateness of exercise, and the level of acceptability in terms of objectives, contents, organizations, graphics and relevance with minimal comments and suggestions from the respondents. Moreover, modular instruction was perceived advantageous and helpful by students and teachers.

Keywords: *development, validation and acceptance, housekeeping, technical vocational livelihood track*

Introduction

The problem and background information that prompted the researcher to carry out this study are described and discussed in this chapter. The problem statement, significance, and the scope and delimitations of the study are all included in the chapter.

One of the teaching tools are modules, which contain a number of organized learning activities intended to aid students in understanding particular objectives. Additionally, it makes information acquisition for pupils more methodical and useful. The usage of modules promotes independent study, especially when it comes to students' development of stronger self-study or learning skills. Housekeeping is one of the Senior High School skill-related tracks, thus it's critical that students have access to high-quality educational resources. According to Abarro (2004), a well-developed instructional resource will significantly improve students' performance and make learning simpler and more long-lasting.

There is no denying that textbooks are still a crucial component of any educational system. Explicit learning was used to take teachings straight out of books. The traditional method's major drawback is that it treats students as empty canvases that the teacher

will fill with knowledge. Salazar (2018) asserted that by creating modules that support what the students can do at the conclusion of the learning program, the K-12 educational systems will transition to an outcome-based approach to teaching. In support to this, Yap (2009) emphasized that modular instruction may offer a solution to the issue of supplementary textbook readings in the teaching of the Housekeeping subject.

How to ensure that students learn effectively and efficiently and how to develop them well-competent holistically is one of the biggest challenges during senior high school years. Concerns about instruction, or the caliber of education one receives, are voiced by both teachers and students. Teachers frequently employ verbal tactics that are occasionally meaningless since they are unable to provide pupils with real, direct, and first-hand experiences (Yap, 2009). The use of words alone cannot and will not produce vivid learning experiences, as experience has shown. To make learning easier to understand, module instruction must be used and chosen carefully.

This issue is prevalent in the teaching of housekeeping to senior high school students. According to the researcher's observations, issues arise in the teaching-learning process for both students and teachers. In this situation, using modules for instruction may be able to offer solutions in place of further textbook readings. In

this manner, the student may manage his time and only ask the instructor for advice as he progresses through the module. Whether or not he learns quickly, the teacher may provide him one-on-one attention without upsetting the other students. It is true that most teachers spend a lot of time looking for, choosing, assessing, changing, and creating materials to use in their lessons (Litz, 2001, as cited in Mengesia and Silassie, 2015). The amount of time that students have to learn is diminished by the activities of many teachers, such as attending seminars, performing other ancillary services, and an unknown number of class cancellations due to various weather disturbances. Lessons are therefore not delivered as scheduled and are frequently interrupted for reasons beyond the teachers' control. The researcher's attention was drawn to the issue by these worries.

Good teaching materials not only can improve the conceptual understanding, but also enhance skills such as analyzing, interpreting, summarizing, and solving problems with creative solutions (Barron and Hammond, 2008). These abilities are very much needed in this modern era (Muqodas et al., 2015). According to the preceding argument, the learning process must be optimized by creating modules with the proper components to inspire students to study in order to strengthen the teaching-learning process, as well as to fulfill the demands of the teachers and students.

Moreover, the Department of Education is mandated by Section 5 of RA No. 10533 to develop the layout and specifics of the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum. For Filipino graduates to be globally competitive, the DepEd shall collaborate with the CHED and TESDA to develop standardized basic, post-secondary, and technical-vocational education curricula. After finishing the track in Grade 12, Housekeeping students in the Senior High School education are expected to take a National Assessment through TESDA. Hence, Housekeeping teachers must ensure that their students have the required competencies to ensure that they will pass the assessment. Learning would be more relevant if the learning strategies and instructional materials used in senior high school should not only comply with the DepEd Curriculum Guide, but also with the TESDA training regulations. It is important that the daily teaching-learning process includes the learning competencies from the DepEd curriculum guide and the competency standard from the Training Regulations from TESDA. The TVL track students would receive training that would enable them to successfully complete the requirements for

qualifications at Levels 1 and 2, as well as under unique situations. Through the development of a module in Housekeeping that provides the competencies required by the DepEd curriculum guide and the TESDA training regulations, learning will be more meaningful. The unavailability of module in Housekeeping as experienced by TVL teachers in the Division of Marinduque prompted the researcher to pursue this developmental study.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to develop a module in Housekeeping and determine its validity and acceptability by TESDA experts from Housekeeping, Cookery, and Bartending specialization, TVL/TLE Supervisor, and teachers in Senior High School teaching Technical Vocational Livelihood Track in the Division of Marinduque. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How is the learning module in Housekeeping for senior high school developed in terms of comparison of learning competencies between DepEd curriculum guide and TESDA training regulation?
2. What is the level of validity of the developed module in terms of:
 - 2.1 Content;
 - 2.2 Organization;
 - 2.3 Relevance;
 - 2.4 Clarity; and
 - 2.5 Appropriateness of Exercise?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the developed module in terms of:
 - 3.1 Objectives;
 - 3.2 Contents;
 - 3.3 Organization;
 - 3.4 Graphics; and
 - 3.5 Relevance?
4. What improved module could be produced by the researcher based on the validation made?

Methodology

This section describes several data collection and analysis strategies that were used that are relevant to the study. population and sample, research instruments, data collection methods, and ethical considerations.

Participants

The module was evaluated by 30 TVL teachers teaching different strands from the 19 schools offering TVL track, three from TESDA experts in tourism sector specialized in Housekeeping, Cookery and Bartending, and one Education Program Supervisor in TVL. The 30 TVL teachers were sampled from 35 TVL teachers in the Division of Marinduque, while the three TESDA experts were sampled from six tourism experts available in Torrijos Poblacion School of Arts and Trade. Torrijos Poblacion School of Arts and Trade is the only TESDA school that offers Housekeeping.

Instruments of the Study

The DepEd curriculum guide and the Training Regulations from TESDA provided information and guided the design and development of the module. The DepEd curriculum guide's learning competencies as well as the competency standards listed in the Training Regulations were taken into account when creating the module's content, teaching-learning methods, and assessment approaches.

In addition, a questionnaire for the modules' validity and acceptability assessment was designed for this study adapting the instruments designed by Malabayabas (2019) and Rebistual (2018). The checklist that Malabayabas (2019) used to determine the validity of an instructional material was adapted to measure the module's validity. Furthermore, in order to evaluate the module's acceptability, the instrument used by Rebistual (2018) was employed.

A Likert Scale of 1 to 5 was provided for every indicator in the instrument. The following are the description of each rating scale.

Modules' Validity:

1. The indicator was 0% to 21% not valid. (The module is not relevant to the learning objectives).
2. The indicator was 21% to 40% least valid. (The module does not meet the required standard based on learning objectives.)
3. The indicator was 41% to 60% moderately valid. (The module provide the required standards but not fully satisfy the learning objectives.)
4. The indicator was 61% to 80% much valid. (The module fully met the required standards based on learning objectives.)
5. The indicator was 81% to 100% very much valid. (The module exceeds the required standards based on

learning objectives.)

Modules' Acceptability:

1. The indicator was 0% to 21% not acceptable. (The module is not relevant to the learning objectives).
2. The indicator was 21% to 40% fairly acceptable. (The module does not meet the required standards based on learning objectives).
3. The indicator was 41% to 60% acceptable. (The module provide the required standards based on learning objectives).
4. The indicator was 61% to 80% moderately acceptable. (The module fully met the required standards based on learning objectives).
5. The indicator was 81% to 100% highly acceptable. (The module exceeds the required standards based on learning objectives).

Procedure

In this study, the ADDIE instructional method was used, however only the Implementation step was disregarded. Analyze, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation is the acronym for ADDIE. The goals and objectives are established, the learning environment is chosen, the instructional obstacles are made evident, and the learner's prior knowledge and skills are noted during the analysis phase. The design process takes into account learning objectives, assessment tools, activities, content, subject matter analysis, lesson preparation, and concept organization. It is important to follow a thorough and exact design approach. The module is built and assembled by the researcher during the development stage. During this phase, a number of tests are created, content is written, and graphics are designed.

The module does not apply to the implementation stage because it only focuses on development, validity, and acceptance. The validity and acceptance of the module were evaluated during the evaluation phase by TVL teachers from several strands, the TVL supervisor, and TESDA specialists from the specializations of housekeeping, cookery, and bartending. Data gathering was conducted from August to November, 2022. The respondents were asked to answer the validity and acceptability assessment questionnaire. Hard copy of the questionnaire was provided to them and they answered at their convenient time. Then the questionnaires were retrieved afterwards. Approval from the office of the SDS and offices of different District supervisors were sought prior to data gathering.

Ethical Considerations

The participant's integrity, confidentiality, and health and safety were all preserved and guaranteed by the researcher at all times, from the start of the study until its completion. The validity and acceptability assessment questionnaire were given to the respondents. They were given a hard copy of the questionnaire, which they completed whenever it was convenient for them. After then, the questionnaires were retrieved. Prior to gathering data, approval from the SDS office and the offices of the various District Supervisors was requested.

Results

The purpose of this study is to design and develop a housekeeping module and evaluate its acceptance and validity. The information that has been obtained, arranged, evaluated, and carefully interpreted to provide answers to the problems is presented in this chapter. The results are shown in tables and figures corresponding with the problem statements stated in Chapter 1.

Module Development Process

Figure 1. *Module Development Process*

The needs of the teachers and the students were assessed during the analysis phase. It was found that the teaching-learning process lacks a module on housekeeping. As the researcher knew from experience, several references were looked up. Due to the lack of consistency in the material provided to the students, they tend to fail the TESDA's national examination. The researcher decided to analyze the required tasks in order to ensure compliance with the DepEd and TESDA-set learning outcomes.

In the Development phase, topics to be included in the module were selected based on the coverage per quarters. Content and activities are sequenced, presented and reinforced. Objectives per week or

session were plotted. Expected skills and outcomes to be achieved by the students were set. Comparison of learning approaches and assessment methods using the DepEd curriculum guide and TESDA's Housekeeping Training Regulation were done to identify what should be included in the module.

During the design phase, learning competencies or objectives as well as information on the subject were written. Based on an examination of the instructional strategies used in the DepEd curriculum guide and the TESDA's Housekeeping training regulation, assessment techniques were created. The design of the contents and activities followed the development phase's planned sequencing. A variety of sites were found to support the data required for the module.

Learning Module Design

Section 3 of the TESDA Training Regulations in Housekeeping NC II, which served as the basis for the learning strategy used to develop a module for housekeeping, contains information on the curriculum design, training delivery, trainee entry requirements, tools and equipment, training facilities, and trainer's qualifications. The creation of the module was based on the methodology and evaluation plan described in the training requirements. The lecture-discussion-interaction structure of the module's information sheet, the interaction of the task sets provided, and the demonstration-based performance task evaluation all fit within this description. The curriculum also includes examples of the evaluation techniques that were covered by the training regulations, including interviews and questions, written tests, and demonstrations. According to section 3.2 of the TESDA Training Regulation in Housekeeping NC II, which was the training delivery, learning is modular in structure, customizable, and self-paced.

Authentic experiences, like a simulation during a performance evaluation, allow students the chance to put new knowledge and skills into practice in a setting that closely reflects the circumstances in which they would apply them. All of these tactics are taken into consideration when developing the learning modules.

The comparison of the learning competencies in the DepEd Housekeeping Curriculum Guide and the TESDA's Housekeeping Training Regulations are shown in Table 3. This also illustrates the instructional strategies applied to each topic in the module.

Table 1. *Comparison of Housekeeping Competencies from DepEd Curriculum Guide and TESDA Training*

Regulation with its Proposed Module Number (see appendix)

This indicates that the fundamental abilities from the Housekeeping training requirements are closely related to the learning competencies established by the DepEd curriculum guide. The module's instructional strategies were based on TESDA's method of assessment.

Evaluation of the Module’s Validity

Five separate parameters are used to evaluate the validity of the module. The requirements for the validity of a module are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2. Parameters used in evaluating the module’s validity

Level of Validity in Terms of Content

The information on the module's content validity is shown in Table 5. As can be seen from the table, the indicator *"the contents of the module are aligned with the learning competencies in the K to 12 Curriculum for Housekeeping NC II"* received a rating of 4.74, which is interpreted as “Very Much Valid” with standard deviation of 0.519 and was perceived to be reliable. This implies that the module's content is consistent with the requirements of the program. With a mean grade of 4.79, it is thought that the *"module used simple and clear directions/instruction"* is "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.404 with a level of high reliability. The module *"may provide insights and ideas on what the activities/exercises are all about,"* according to the mean evaluation of 4.79, which has a verbal interpretation of "Very Much Valid" and has a standard deviation of 0.446 with a

level of high reliability. Additionally, the module's ability to *"give background of concepts and information about the topic to be solved"* received a rating of 4.79 and an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" and with standard deviation of 0.404 with a level of high reliability also. With an interpretation of "Very Much Valid," *"the module can arouse students' interest to perform the tasks,"* as indicated by the mean rating of 4.68 with standard deviation of 0.544 with a level of reliable. According to the data, the content of the module is "Very Much Valid," with a grand mean of 4.75 and average standard deviation of 0.463 with a level of high reliability.

Table 2. Level of Validity in Terms of Content

Content	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The contents of the module are aligned with the learning competencies in the K to 12 Curriculum for Housekeeping NC II.	4.74	0.519	Very Much Valid
The module used simple and clear directions/instruction.	4.79	0.404	Very Much Valid
The module can provide insights and ideas on what the activities/exercises are all about.	4.79	0.446	Very Much Valid
The module can provide background of concepts and information about the topic to be solved.	4.79	0.404	Very Much Valid
The module can arouse students' interest to perform the tasks.	4.68	0.544	Very Much Valid
General Average	4.75	0.463	Very Much Valid

According to Roman's (2016) study, the developed module's content with a grand mean of 4.70 indicates that it is "Very Much Valid." His responses deemed it crucial that the module's content be in line with the curriculum. According to Noah and Ahmad (2005), a module will be considered to be good if its content validity is high.

Level of Validity in Terms of Organization

The information about the validity level in terms of its organization is shown in Table 6. The interpretation of *"The module has well-organized exercises/activities arranged from simple to complex"* is "Very Much Valid" with a mean of 4.62 with standard deviation of 0.604. The produced module received a weighted mean of 4.62 with regard to *"the module is sequenced accordingly; it starts with concept, explanation of concepts, examples, a series of exercises,"* indicating that they are "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.486. With an interpretation of “Very Much Valid,” the third indicator, *"the module is well-constructed; it has parts such as title page, learning*

competencies, module number, week number, and the content," received a weighted mean of 4.62 with standard deviation of 0.486. It means that the module follows the order required by the students' relevant learning strategy. For the indicator "the module has logical sequence of concepts and exercises", it has a rating of 4.74 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.504. The last indicator which is "the topics fit the sequence of the learning competencies in the K to 12 curriculum", has a weighted mean of 4.79 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" as well with standard deviation of 0.404.

The general mean of the created module's organizational validity is 4.68, which indicates that, in the respondents' perspective, the module's lesson organization is "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.497 indicating high reliability.

Table 3. Level of Validity in Terms of Organization

Organization	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
The module has well-organized exercises/activities arranged from simple to complex.	4.62	0.604	Very Much Valid
The module is sequenced accordingly; it starts with concept, explanation of concepts, examples, a series of exercises.	4.62	0.486	Very Much Valid
The module is well-constructed; it has parts such as title page, learning competencies, module number, week number, and the content.	4.62	0.486	Very Much Valid
The module has logical sequence of concepts and exercises.	4.74	0.504	Very Much Valid
The topics fit the sequence of the learning competencies in the K to 12 curriculum.	4.79	0.404	Very Much Valid
General Average	4.68	0.497	Very Much Valid

In Olivar's (2019) study, his manual was arranged from an overview of work ethics through professionalism and productivity, and it received a general weighted mean of 4.49, translating to "Very Much Valid." It is very evident that the designed module, which consists of many courses and corresponding activities, must be extremely well arranged in accordance with the learning skills that the students are required to meet.

According to the module's assessment, the respondent's statement that "the module is well organized and well done" is well supported by the

following arguments.

Level of Validity in Terms of Relevance

In terms of module's relevance, the indicator "the activities/exercises can present practical application of skill to real situation" got a mean rating of 4.59 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.549. The indicator that "the activities/exercises can be relevant, interesting, contextualized, localized and self-motivating to the learner", was also found "Very Much Valid" with a mean rating of 4.62 with standard deviation of 0.486. The indicator "the activities/exercises can seek to related new concepts from previous learning" got a mean rating of 4.65 equivalent to the verbal interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.557, while the indicator "the activities/exercises stimulates the learner to relevant activities" got a mean rating of 4.65 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" as well with standard deviation of 0.536.

The overall mean of the level of validity in terms of module relevance is 4.63, which indicates that, in the respondents' opinion, the module's relevance is "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.532 indicating reliable level. According to the results, the respondents thought the modules were excellent educational resources for teaching students.

Table 4. Level of Validity in Terms of Relevance

Relevance	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The activities/exercises can present practical application of skill to real situation.	4.59	0.549	Very Much Valid
2. The activities/exercises can be relevant, interesting, contextualized, localized and self-motivating to the learner	4.62	0.486	Very Much Valid
3. The activities/exercises can seek to related new concepts from previous learning	4.65	0.557	Very Much Valid
4. The activities/exercises stimulates the learner to relevant activities	4.65	0.536	Very Much Valid
General Average	4.63	0.532	Very Much Valid

According to the respondents' evaluations and validations, it is clear that the generated module is relevant to the current educational system. When it comes to topics and competences that are related to skills, a module that was created locally and culturally is relevant.

According to Olivar's (2019) study, his module's relevance increased to a total weighted mean of 4.59 and was interpreted as "Very Much Valid." If a module includes accurate tasks and exercises, it indicates that it is relevant.

Level of Validity in Terms of Clarity

In terms of module's clarity, "the module has clear and simple concepts, ideas, and directions" got a mean rating of 4.74 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.504. The indicator that "the language is clear and easy to understand", was also found "Very Much Valid" with a mean rating of 4.59 with standard deviation of 0.628. The indicator "the concept for each activity is arrange logically to ensure that there is no duplication" got a mean rating of 4.67 equivalent to the verbal interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.471, while on the indicator "the structure, style, content, and format should be appropriate to the target level of learners" got a score of 4.67 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" also and with standard deviation of 0.471.

The general mean of the module's clarity score is 4.67, which indicates that, in the respondents' opinion, the module's lesson's clarity is "Very Much Valid" with an average standard deviation of 0.519 with reliable level.

However, the respondents also stated that "pictures of step-by-step procedures in the activities may add clarity and will provide the learners with exact procedure for a certain performance activity," which suggests that there is still room for improvement in the developed module's clarity.

Table 5. Level of Validity in Terms of Clarity

Clarity	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. The module has clear and simple concepts, ideas, and directions.	4.74	0.504	Very Much Valid
2. The language is clear and easy to understand.	4.59	0.628	Very Much Valid
3. The concept for each activity is arrange logically to ensure that there is no duplication.	4.67	0.471	Very Much Valid
4. The structure, style, content, and format should be appropriate to the target level of learners.	4.67	0.471	Very Much Valid
General Average	4.67	0.519	Very Much Valid

When creating a concise and clear concept, language, ideas, and structure for the module, consideration must be given to the learners' learning capacities, learning preferences, and degree of knowledge. According to Salazar's (2018) study, the module's clarity must be given with clear information and language to facilitate learning.

Level of Validity in Terms of Appropriateness of Exercise

In terms of module's appropriateness of exercise, the indicator "the activities/exercises take in consideration the varying attitudes and capabilities of the learners" got a mean rating of 4.56 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" with standard deviation of 0.553. The indicator that "The activities/exercises are suitable to the different classroom setting either modular or face to face", was also found "Very Much Valid" with a mean rating of 4.5 and standard deviation of 0.606. The indicator "There is an enrichment activity that is adaptable to classes with multiple number of students" got a mean rating of 4.71 equivalent to the verbal interpretation of "Very Much Valid" and standard deviation of 0.456, while on the indicator "The module provides opportunity for the development and enhancement of Housekeeping NC II skills" got a mean rating of 4.71 with an interpretation of "Very Much Valid" as well and standard deviation of 0.516.

The overall mean of the level of validity for the appropriateness of the exercise in the module is 4.62, and standard deviation of 0.533 which signifies that, in the respondents' view, the appropriateness of the activity in the module is "Very Much Valid" and reliable. This indicates that, in general the modules are excellent learning resources that can assist instruction, as evidenced by the high ratings of the respondents.

On the other hand, respondents recommended that "learners should be given more practical activities, and a performance checklist should be made available to precisely measure the intended output of the learners," which suggests also that there is still room for improvement in the developed module's appropriateness of exercise.

Table 6. *Level of Validity in Terms of Appropriateness of Exercise*

<i>Appropriateness Of Exercise</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The activities/exercises take in consideration the varying attitudes and capabilities of the learners.	4.56	0.553	Very Much Valid
2. The activities/exercises are suitable to the different classroom setting either modular or face to face.	4.5	0.606	Very Much Valid
3. There is an enrichment activity that is adaptable to classes with multiple number of students.	4.71	0.456	Very Much Valid
4. The module provides opportunity for the development and enhancement of Housekeeping NC II skills.	4.71	0.516	Very Much Valid
General Average	4.62	0.533	Very Much Valid

The exercises' suitability depends on the learning skills that the students need to acquire. It must be consistent with the desired goals. Any type of evaluation will serve as exercise, but it must always be led by the learning goals that need to be completed.

Students can thoroughly learn from, comprehend, and respond to the guide questions in the study of Laroza (2015) by going over the examples and illustrations that are included for each topic in the exercises.

Summary of Rating for the Level of Validity of the Developed Module

The content, organization, relevance, clarity, and appropriateness of the exercise were all rated for validity in the developed module, with an overall mean value of 4.68 and a verbal interpretation of Very Much Valid. In detail, content got a mean rating of 4.75 with standard deviation of 0.463, organization got a mean rating of 4.68 with standard deviation of 0.497, relevance got a mean rating of 4.63 with standard deviation of 0.532, clarity got a mean rating of 4.69 with standard deviation of 0.519 and appropriateness of exercise got a mean rating of 4.63 with standard deviation of 0.533. This implies that a set of values has a low degree of dispersion, which suggests that they are close to the mean. This indicates that the answers provided by the respondents are highly connected to one another.

Table 7. *Summary of Rating for the Level of Validity of the Developed Module*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Content	4.75	0.463	Very Much Valid
Organization	4.68	0.497	Very Much Valid
Relevance	4.63	0.532	Very Much Valid
Clarity	4.69	0.519	Very Much Valid
Appropriateness of Exercise	4.63	0.533	Very Much Valid
Overall	4.68	0.509	Very Much Valid

The designed module in housekeeping was often given a verbal interpretation of "Very Much Valid" by TVL teachers and expert respondents. It indicates that the Housekeeping module was developed in accordance with the standards of validity in terms of the content, organization, relevance, clarity, and appropriateness of exercise. As they stated, "the content is well organized and the activities are arranged from simple to complex. It can arouse the student's interest to perform the tasks," they see the following supporting points as being very much valid.

Overall, validation surveys suggest that the content was perceived to be of high quality, with high mean scores across all dimensions. The standard deviations were also generally small, indicating that the ratings were consistent across respondents.

Level of Acceptability of the Module

The respondents evaluated the module's acceptability based on its objectives, contents, organization, graphics, and relevance. The parameters used to determine whether or not the module was acceptable are shown in the figure below.

Figure 3. *Parameters used in evaluation the module's acceptability*

Level of Acceptability in Terms of Objectives

The results are shown in Table 11 regarding the level of acceptance of the produced module in terms of its objectives. The mean rating of 4.82 indicates that the objectives are "very acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.382 and that the module's lessons are "specific." With a mean grade of 4.74, the objectives in the lessons of the module "are measurable and results-oriented" are deemed to be "very satisfactory" with standard deviation of 0.441. The target outlined in the module's lessons is "attainable" according to the mean evaluation of 4.74, which has a verbal interpretation of "very acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.441. Additionally, the purpose of the module's lessons, "time bounded," had a mean rating of 4.71, with standard deviation of 0.456 which is also quite respectable.

The surveys show that the module's objectives are "very acceptable," with a grand mean rating of 4.75 with standard deviation of 0.430.

Table 8. *Level of Acceptability in Terms of Objectives*

<i>The objective stated in the lessons of the module</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. are specific	4.82	0.382	Highly Acceptable
2. are measurable and results-oriented.	4.74	0.441	Highly Acceptable
3. are attainable.	4.74	0.441	Highly Acceptable
4. are time bounded.	4.71	0.456	Highly Acceptable
General Average	4.75	0.430	Highly Acceptable

The respondents' level of acceptance of the module's objectives is nearly identical to the outcome of Rebistual's (2018) study, which he characterized as "Highly Acceptable," indicating that all respondents found the objectives to their complete satisfaction with a general mean of 4.74.

The module must be accompanied by a distinct learning objective, as Donnelly and Fitzmaurice (2005) noted, so that students are aware of what they must do after engaging in the learning process. The fundamental structure of the module is composed of learning objectives, learning goals, resources, teaching and learning strategies, assessment standards, and evaluation.

Level of Acceptability in Terms of Contents

Data in Table 12 reveal that the respondents gave the module's lessons a rating of 4.82, which indicates that they are "very acceptable" and that they "are based on

prescribed/expected abilities" with standard deviation of 0.381. The respondents gave the module's content a mean rating of 4.79, which they interpreted as "Very Acceptable" since they "provide varied exercises and activities" with standard deviation of 0.404. The third indicator, "explained and discussed extensively" in the module's lesson, received a mean rating of 4.53 and a verbal interpretation of "Very Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.499. With a verbal interpretation of "Highly Acceptable," the indicator "the lessons in the module are discussed comprehensively enough for the timeframe" had a mean rating of 4.71 with standard deviation of 0.456. With a grand mean of 4.71, all indicators of the module's content were deemed to be "Highly Acceptable" with an average standard deviation of 0.435. This value indicates a very low dispersion of the scores according to the interpretive scale.

Table 9. *Level of Acceptability in Terms of Contents*

<i>The lesson in the module</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. are based on prescribed/expected competencies.	4.82	0.381	Highly Acceptable
2. provide for varied exercises and activities.	4.79	0.404	Highly Acceptable
3. are explained and discussed extensively.	4.53	0.499	Highly Acceptable
4. are discussed comprehensively enough for the timeframe.	4.71	0.456	Highly Acceptable
General Average	4.71	0.435	Highly Acceptable

In the study of Salazar (2018) the content of the module with the grand mean rating of 4.49 that has a corresponding verbal interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" was that the "contents of each lesson effects the most important aspects of what is being taught". The content leads to the attainment of the objectives. In the study of Roman (2016), it was emphasized that the content contributes to the assessment of the module's validity.

Level of Acceptability in Terms of Organization

The acceptability of the generated module in terms of organization is shown in Table 13. With an interpretation of "Highly Acceptable," the indicator "the lessons covered and discussed equitably" had a mean rating of 4.65 with standard deviation of 0.478 indicating very low dispersion. With a mean rating of 4.62, the indicator that "the lessons covered provide checking of prerequisite skills" was likewise deemed

to be "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.486 indicating very low dispersion also. The indicator *"the lessons are arranged logically and sequentially"* received a mean rating of 4.71 and a verbal interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" with a mean rating of 0.518 showing low dispersion, while the indicator *"the lessons are applied to other disciplines"* received a mean rating of 4.74 with standard deviation of 0.441 indicating very low dispersion. With a grand mean of 4.68 with standard deviation of 0.481 all indicators of the module's organization were deemed to be "Highly Acceptable" indicating very low dispersion of scores according to interpretive scale.

Table 10. *Level of Acceptability in Terms of Organization*

<i>The lessons covered</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. are discussed equitably.	4.65	0.478	Highly Acceptable
2. provide checking of prerequisite skills.	4.62	0.486	Highly Acceptable
3. are arranged logically and sequentially.	4.71	0.518	Highly Acceptable
4. are applied to other disciplines.	4.74	0.441	Highly Acceptable
General Average	4.68	0.481	Highly Acceptable

The lesson content of the module has been compromised down into different elements and ideas that make it easier for students to understand. It is also given in a variety of ways with a wide range of pre requisite activities to fit different learning styles and aptitudes. The module's content may be written in its entirety or the student may be given resources and references to deepen their understanding of the module's topic.

According to (Omer et al., 2001), module is said to be organized when it is constructed in many logical ways in accordance with the nature of the subject matter and the characteristics of the students it is intended for, such as from simple to complex. From the known to the unknown, from facts and fragmented knowledge to laws and comprehensive relationships, from the whole to the part, and from the ancient to the contemporary, which are arranged logically and sequentially.

Level of Acceptability in Terms of Graphics

The indicator *"the pictures, figures, diagrams and tables clearly convey the idea or thoughts in the pictures, figures, and tables"* received a mean rating of

4.71 and was interpreted as "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.457 in terms of the module's graphics. With a mean rating of 4.65 and standard deviation of 0.478, the signal *"the pictures, figures, diagrams and tables are appropriate for the lessons at hand"* was likewise rated as "Highly Acceptable" with very low dispersion of scores. The indicator *"the pictures, figures, diagrams and tables are originally crafted by the author"* received a mean rating of 4.56 and a verbal interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.496 while the indicator *"the pictures, figures, diagrams and tables are presented with vivid colors"* received a mean rating of 4.71 equivalent to the interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.456 indicating very low dispersion of scores.

The graphics of the module's content are "Highly Acceptable," according to the respondents, as seen by the module's overall mean acceptability rating of 4.6 with standard deviation of 0.472.

Table 11. *Level of Acceptability in Terms of Graphics*

<i>The pictures, figures, diagrams and tables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. clearly convey the idea or thoughts in the pictures, figures and tables.	4.71	0.457	Highly Acceptable
2. are appropriate for the lessons at hand	4.65	0.478	Highly Acceptable
3. are originally crafted by the author.	4.56	0.496	Highly Acceptable
4. are presented with vivid colors.	4.71	0.456	Highly Acceptable
General Average	4.6	0.472	Highly Acceptable

The study by Lai and Neuby (2012) found that the graphic's quality can affect how it is interpreted and the benefits derived from using it. The notion that genuine learning happens when students voluntarily choose pertinent information, arrange it into understandable representations, and combine it with existing knowledge. Pictures and other visuals assist decrease the need for extended textual descriptions. Understanding, inference, prospective discovery, and learner motivation can all be enhanced by graphics.

Level of Acceptability in Terms of Relevance

For module relevancy, the indicator *"the lessons provide real-life scenarios applicable to the students' subsequent actual work"* received a mean rating of 4.76 which meant that it was "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.424 meaning the score has very low dispersion. The respondents gave a mean

rating of 4.59, which is interpreted as "Highly Acceptable," for the indicator referring to the lessons that are "according to the new educational paradigm with standard deviation of 0.534 interpreted as low dispersion of scores. Meanwhile, the third indicator, "the lesson in the module are easy to comprehend and applicable to daily life situations," received a mean rating of 4.82 with an interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.381 indicating very low dispersion of scores. The fourth indicator the module was designed to give students the opportunity to learn and study independently has a mean rating of 4.76, which is also interpreted as "Highly Acceptable" with standard deviation of 0.424 indicating very low dispersion of scores too.

The indicator "the lesson in the module are easy to comprehend and applicable to daily life situations" received the highest rating of 4.82, meanwhile "the lessons accord to the new education paradigm" had the lowest rating of 4.59, though both ratings still signify that the module's relevance is "Highly Acceptable."

With a grand mean of 4.73 with standard deviation of 0.441, all indicators of the module's relevance that were evaluated and validated were determined to be "Highly Acceptable" with very low dispersion of scores, and said to be with high reliability level.

Table 12. Level of Acceptability in Terms of Relevance

The lessons	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. provide real-life scenarios applicable to the student's subsequent actual work.	4.76	0.424	Highly Acceptable
2. accord to the new education paradigm.	4.59	0.534	Highly Acceptable
3. are easy to comprehend and applicable to daily life situations.	4.82	0.381	Highly Acceptable
4. create opportunity for students to learn and study with independency.	4.76	0.424	Highly Acceptable
General Average	4.73	0.441	Highly Acceptable

Relevance is the notion that two subjects are connected in a way that makes it advantageous to consider the second issue when considering the first. It is also known as how the data relates to current situations. This is comparable to the research by Biggs and Tang (2007), which found that each component is "aligned" and complements the others if students can connect its content to a real-world situation. According to him, the material is presented in a way that makes sense and is

connected to the stated objectives, outcomes, and evaluation procedure.

Summary of Rating for the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Module

Table 16 reveals the summary of rating for the level of acceptability of the Developed Module in terms of objectives, content, organization, graphics and relevance. It has an overall mean of 4.694 with an interpretation of Highly Acceptable with standard deviation of 0.452. Objectives got a mean rating of 4.75 with standard deviation of 0.430, content got a mean rating of 4.71 with standard deviation of 0.435, organization got a mean rating of 4.68 with standard deviation of 0.481, graphics got a mean rating of 4.6 with standard deviation of 0.472 and relevance got a mean rating of 4.73 with standard deviation of 0.441 and have all an interpretation of "Highly Acceptable".

The objective has its highest reliability with standard deviation of 0.430, content with standard deviation of 0.435 indicates highest reliability also, organization with standard deviation of 0.481 referring to high reliability, graphics with standard deviation of 0.472 which means of high reliability, and relevance with standard deviation of 0.441 indicating high reliability with overall standard deviation of 0.452 which indicate high reliability also according to the interpretative scale.

Table 13. Summary of Rating for the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Module

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Objectives	4.75	0.430	Highly Acceptable
Content	4.71	0.435	Highly Acceptable
Organization	4.68	0.481	Highly Acceptable
Graphics	4.6	0.472	Highly Acceptable
Relevance	4.73	0.441	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.694	0.452	Highly Acceptable

Generally, the developed module in housekeeping assessed by the TVL teachers and expert-respondents has an overall interpretation of "Highly Acceptable" with high reliability level and very low dispersion of scores based on the interpretive scale. This indicates that the developed module complies to a certain level with the objectives, content, organization, graphics, and relevance.

Improved Module in Housekeeping

In order to make this revised module positively

connected with the targeted results for the learners, particularly in teaching activities, assessment, and picture usage, the validators' comments and suggestions were taken into consideration. Additional pictures have been employed in the module's new features to illustrate the content. It is possible to access performance checklists to precisely assess students' intended output. For clarity and to show learners the exact steps to take for each performance exercise, step-by-step pictures of the procedures have been included to the activities. According to research (Carney and Levin, 2002), the use of pictures in the design of instructional activities has a significant impact on both learner motivation and learning outcomes. Pictures and images can either directly convey information to the learner or assist them in understanding relevant text within the lesson. To maximize the effectiveness of visual and graphic resources used in educational activities, design concepts are well-established.

Discussion

The research's principal goal is to develop a module in housekeeping for technical vocational livelihood track of the senior high school education. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the validity and acceptance of the module in housekeeping. The learning module in Housekeeping for Senior High School was developed in terms of comparison of learning competencies between DepEd curriculum guide and TESDA training regulation. Three processes, namely analysis, development, and design, were used to create the module. The developed module evaluated the exercise's validity in terms of its content with mean of 4.74 with a verbal interpretation of very much valid; organization with a mean of 4.68 with a verbal interpretation of very much valid; relevance with a mean of 4.63 with a verbal interpretation of very much valid; clarity with a mean of 4.67 with a verbal interpretation of very much valid; and appropriateness of exercise with a mean of 4.62 with a verbal interpretation of very much valid also.

The level of acceptability of the developed module in terms of objectives has a mean of 4.75 with a verbal interpretation of highly acceptable; contents has a mean of 4.71 with a verbal interpretation of highly acceptable; organization has a mean of 4.68 with a verbal interpretation of highly acceptable; graphics has a mean of 4.6 with a verbal interpretation of highly acceptable; and relevance with a mean of 4.73 with a verbal interpretation of highly acceptable also.

An improved module was produced by the researcher

based on the validation made. The validators' comments and suggestions were taken into account in order to make this redesigned module positively associated with the targeted results for the learners, notably in instructional activities, assessment, and picture usage. The content of the module's new features is illustrated with additional images. To properly assess students planned output, performance checklists are accessible. Step-by-step photographs of the procedures have been included to the activities for clarity and to demonstrate to learners the precise steps to take for each performance practice.

Conclusion

The findings lead to the following conclusions. The TVL teachers, TVL supervisor, and TESDA specialists all evaluated the module on housekeeping to be highly effective. The design of the module's learning strategy complied with TESDA's competency standards as well as the requirements of the teacher-trainers. Students were able to easily relate to their national assessment through this. According to the data gathered, the housekeeping module that was created was very much valid in terms of its content, organization, relevance, clarity, and appropriateness of exercise. According to data gathered from the respondents, the level of acceptability was likewise found to be highly acceptable. Additionally, it was determined that the generated housekeeping module was well regarded and valid by TVL teachers, supervisors, and TESDA specialists.

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Table 1. Comparison of Housekeeping Competencies from DepEd Curriculum Guide and TESDA Training

TESDA Learning Competencies	DepEd Learning Competencies and Objectives		Proposed Module
	Learning Competencies	Learning Objectives	
Provide Housekeeping Services			
Receive housekeeping request		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss implementing Hotel Codes, Rules and regulations 	Module 1 (W1, Q1)
	Handle housekeeping request	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain different skills of good housekeeper needs such as in and intrapersonal skills List down and describe the basic functions of each personnel in the housekeeping department 	Module 2 (W2, Q1)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss nature and scope of guestroom cleaning, care and maintenance Enumerate bedroom and bathroom amenities offered in an institution List down procedures in conducting room check, turn down and make up beds 	Module 3 (W3, Q1)
Provide/Service Housekeeping Requests			
Provide advice to guest		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe and explain the use of different types of housekeeping and front office forms Provide guest orientation on house rules and use of hotel tools, materials, equipment, and other amenities 	Module 4 (W4, Q1)
	Advise guests on room and housekeeping equipment		
Liaise with other departments		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practice proper handling of client's queries through telephone, fax machine, e-mail, etc. Identify common problems related to Housekeeping Services Observe proper handling of different problems in Housekeeping Services 	Module 5 (W5, Q1)
Prepare Rooms for Guests			
Set up equipment and trolleys	Set up equipment and trolleys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and explain the different types and uses of cleaning tools, materials and equipment for room servicing Correctly select and demonstrate proper use of tools, materials and equipment according to task requirement 	Module 6 (W6, Q1)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Properly set trolley/caddy with cleaning materials according to needs and with the institutional standards • Observe safety measures and procedures in handling cleaning tools, equipment, and other supplies 	Module 7 (W7, Q1)
Access rooms for servicing	Access rooms for servicing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify important terminologies used in housekeeping such as room status, door signs, guest's type, and guest room classifications • Observe guests' safety and security in hotel establishment 	Module 8 (W8, Q1)
Make up beds	Make up beds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify different types and sizes of linens, pillows, and bed sheets • Correctly follow proper procedures in conducting room check, turn down and make up beds and cots • Replace bed linen in accordance with establishment standards and procedures 	Module 1 (W1, Q2)
Clean and clear rooms	Clean rooms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify tools, materials, supplies, and equipment needed in cleaning guest rooms • Follow standard operating procedures in institutional cleaning • Identify common insects and pests and their control measures • Give minor and major hotel room defects and repair • Observe hotel management safety practices and procedures 	Module 2 (W2, Q2)

TESDA Learning Competencies	DepEd Learning Competencies and Objectives		Proposed Module
	Learning Competencies	Learning Objectives	
Clean Public Areas, Facilities and Equipment			
Select and set up equipment and materials	Select and set up equipment and materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select appropriate cleaning tools and equipment with their proper uses and functions • Follow safety and security measures when using cleaning tools and equipment • Identify and use dry and wet cleaning agents/chemicals for a particular task • Select and use Personal Protective Equipment based on the task requirement 	Module 3 (W3, Q2)
Apply cleaning technique	Apply cleaning technique	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify cleaning equipment and chemical • Discuss cleaning technique on furniture and walling materials • Follow proper storage of equipment and chemicals 	Module 4 (W4, Q2)

	Clean and store trolleys and equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform proper handling of trolleys and other equipment • Observe proper cleaning of tools, materials, and equipment according to standards and procedures • Practice safekeeping practices in accordance with establishment standards 	Module 5 (W5, Q2)
Clean dry and wet areas	Clean dry and wet areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify common problems related to scheduling and performing one's task • Consider possible inconvenience and hazards in working area • Observe implementing policies and procedures related to cleaning operations • Practice proper disposal of used chemicals in accordance with manufacturer's instructions and environmental legislation requirements 	Module 6 (W6, Q2)
Maintain and store cleaning equipment and chemicals	Maintain and store cleaning equipment and chemicals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use and maintain cleaning tools, materials, and equipment effectively in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions and hotel standards • Perform institutional routine maintenance with standard operating procedures • Identify and report common problems in cleaning tools and equipment • Observe safety procedures in safekeeping of cleaning tools, equipment, and chemicals following the security standards 	Module 7 (W7, Q2)
TESDA Learning Competencies	DepEd Learning Competencies and Objectives		Proposed Module
	Learning Competencies	Learning Objectives	
Provide Valet/Butler Service			
Provide valet services to guests			
Display professional valet standards	Display professional valet standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss basic roles of valet and butler service within the Philippine hospitality industry 	Module 1 (W1, Q3)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish rapport and enhance feelings of goodwill between the guest and the establishment through principles of good communication in accordance with the establishment standards 	Module 2 (W2, Q3)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice good grooming and personal hygiene of valet service provider 	Module 3 (W3, Q3)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow standard operating procedures in keeping laundry area clean in accordance with the establishment standards 	Module 4 (W4, Q3)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare reports and endorsements of valet service provider 	Module 5 (W5, Q3)
Care for guest property	Care for guest property	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform packing, unpacking, storing, and preparing of guest luggage management 	Module 6 (W6, Q3)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe institutional standards in preparing of guest clothes and shoes 	Module 7 (W7, Q3)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make simple repairs on cloth and linen in accordance with the establishment procedures 	Module 8 (W8, Q3)
Laundry Linen and Guest Clothes			
Process laundered item	Process laundry items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and explain types of linen used in housekeeping Discuss the principles of laundering such as collection and transportation, arrival and sorting Give the types and usage of washing machine and dryers used in housekeeping 	Module 1 (W1, Q4)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and discuss the types and usage of laundry chemicals and other cleaning agents Enumerate and discuss the classifications and usage of stain removing agents Explain the wash cycle and its importance 	Module 2 (W2, Q4)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perform laundry methods accordingly Observe principles and procedures in ironing and pressing clothes and linens Explain the types of ironing equipment, tools, and materials and their proper usage Demonstrate correct folding methods and techniques 	Module 3 (W3, Q4)
Collect laundry for laundering functions	Package and store laundry items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify forms needed for packaging and storing of laundry items Explain ideal standards of packaging and storing of laundry items 	Module 4 (W4, Q4)
Perform laundering functions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss the procedures in storing guest laundry in accordance with the establishment standards for 	Module 5 (W5, Q4)
Return laundered item		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observe correct delivery of laundry items to guests 	
Deal with/Handle Intoxicated Guests			
Determine the level of intoxication	Determine level of intoxication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and explain the level of Intoxication Discuss the effects of alcohol and the factors that influence guest's action Follow standard operation procedure in assessing intoxicated guest 	Module 6 (W6, Q4)
Apply appropriate procedures	Apply appropriate procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss DO's and DON'Ts in assisting intoxicated guests Observe proper way of dealing with intoxicated guest Ways in communicating with intoxicated guest 	Module 7 (W7, Q4)

Comply with legislation	Comply with legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Correct way in dealing with intoxicated customers in line with Industry practice• Discuss ways on how to deal with underage drinkers with caution and care in compliance with legal regulation• Identify laws governing the sale of alcohol beverages	Module 8 (W8, Q4)
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